

<p align="center">Definition Criteria of Synonyms in the Uzbek Language</p>		<p align="center">Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: seme, sememe, synonyms, integral seme, differential seme, potential sema, contextual synonyms.</p>
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<p align="center">Abstract</p>		
<p>This article examines the meaningfulness of lexical-semantic relationships. Polysemic lexemes were studied in the synonymy seme and synonyms of sememe which are derived from the meaning of grammar and polysememic lexemes. Synonymic sememes and synonyms are different from lexical synonyms. The grammatical synonyms, context synonyms, complete synonyms, the spiritual synonyms, methodological synonyms, as well as the grammar and lexical units within polysememic lexemes have been studied. There are examples of meaningful words and meaningful additions to grammatical synonyms. Lexical synonyms and affixes synonyms are derived from linguistic units. Syntactic synonyms have been studied in terms of the combination of words, fixed connections and phrases. Synonyms were analyzed based on metaphora, metonymy, and synecdoche. The Synonym semes are divided into several types depending on the lexical meaning, the morphem composition, the grammatical meaning of the semantic space, the syntactic relationship, and the synonym syllabus based on this classification. The synonymy of denotative sema, conotativesema, core seme, deravativeseme, relative seme, intermediate seme, integral seme, differential seme, potential seme, grammatical syllabus were studied. The notion of synopsis of polynomials within the framework of the lexems is derived from the meaning of meaning, portable meaning, figural meaning, syntactic meaning, constructive meaning, meanings. Synonyms have been analyzed by the metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and portable expressions. There are examples and conclusions about the types of synonyms and their emergence within the context of polysememic lexis.</p>		

Synonyms have been widely studied in Uzbek linguistics. Almost all of the synonyms are focused on the closeness, the unity of meaning. “Synonymy means the same phenomenon, and the synonym is the language units with the same meaning” [9, p. 122]. “The key condition for multiple words to be synonymous is the same, uniformity, mutual proximity or similarity in meaning” [4, p. 190]. “Synonymy is also found in both the linguistic units and grammatical units” [7, p. 108]. For the first time in the term grammatical synonyms used the M.Peshkovsky [5, p. 188]. The synonymy of grammatical units is divided into the following types:

1. Words that are meaningful (synonymous words) – the conjunctions *negaki*, *chunki* are represent the meaning of the cause. It's a synonym words. These words do not represent a lexical meaning, so synonymous is not a lexem. Synonymic lexics can be used with the term meaningful words. But grammatically synonymous words can not be learned under the terms of synonymic lexemes.

2. Synonymic affixes. The affixes *-ish*, *-larin* the words *borishdi*, *bordilar* are substitute grammatical meanings, such as common and plural. Accordingly, they are meaningful additions.

3. The meaning of words and sentences. Internetdanjo‘natdik. Internet orqalijo‘natdik. The word *orqali* and the affix *-dan* are mean the way, that is through. Accordingly, they can be meaningful.

The synonyms in the lexical units is as follows:

1. Lexical synonyms. The *baland* and *ulkan* words are from the synonymy according to calling mean. These lexemes are linguistically meaningful in terms of size. The lexical synonyms are divided into two. 1. Complete (absolute) synonyms. 2. Meaningful (semantic) synonyms. It should be noted that G.M. Ismoilov in his work on the study of synonyms in terminology, in short, substituting the absolute synonym term with the principle of expressing the word correctly, refer to the terms of doublet synonym [3, p. 123-124].

2. Affix synonyms. The affixes *-er-*, *-li* are considered affix synonyms because the affixes the same meaning to the word. For example, *gulli*, *sergul*. These synonyms are also studied as single-synonyms [11, p. 11]. Adding words can also create synonyms. For example, the *bulutday*, *barmoqday* are synonymous with "big", "large" synonyms, but not synonymous with a list of syntax errors: 1. "*Ostingdabulutdayot, egning but*" (Oybek "Navoi"). 2. "*barmoqday-barmoqdayuzumlar*". Such a meaningful attitude is characteristic of polysememic lexemes.

Polysememic lexemes are studied in the linguistics. Therefore, it is possible to observe the synonymy of the polisemic lexem or the synonymy seme and synonymy sememe that emerge within polysememic lexemes. For example, *bema'ni*, *bemazapolymemem* lexemes are not synonymous with the main meanings, but in their other meanings, they are the same: *bema'niodam*, *bemazaodam* (meaning "bad", "mischief" man), *bema'niqiliq*, *bemazaqiliq* (it mean the "refers to morals", "except for the innocent"). *Bema'ni*, *bemaza* lexemes can be synonymous with a synonym word, but can not form a list of lexical synonyms, but can be synonymous with the same synonyms as used in portable sense. Such a sense of meaning creates synonymic sememes. *Mehnatimizningmahsuli*, *mehnatimizningmevasi*. *Mahsul* and *meva* polysemantically lexemes form synonymic seme such as "result", "effectiveness" in the combination, and thus are more meaningful. Such synonymic seme lexemes are ineffective in the speech, and some of the sememe contents are meaningless.

Synonymy also exists in the general meaning of the words and phrases. Such synonyms in language are called syntactic synonyms.

1. The meaning of the word combination.

a) A free combination: *tiliyomonodam*, *tiliachchiqodam*, *tilizaharodam*. synonymic syllables within the context of lexemes vispolysemanticlexemes: *tilizaharodam*, *chayonodam*, *ilonodam*.

b) A synonymy in the phraseology: *og'ziqulog'ida*, *do'ppisinomongaotmoq*. Such synonyms are called phraseological synonyms.

2) Syntactic synonyms. *Maqsadimshu: men shifokorbo 'lmoqchiman. Maqsadimshuki, men shifokorbo 'lmoqchiman.*

Contextual synonymy. “Contextual synonymy has a variety of views. This kind of synonymic attitude happens every time in the conversation, and it goes beyond the obvious speech” [7, p. 118].

For example, *Kozimilgariochilganbolsaedi, man yuragimniborilargayedirarmidim? Qizim, kechir, buadashgan, kordadangnikechir!* (English: if my eyes were previously opened, would I have made my heart to wolves? My daughter, forgive this blind, blind man!) (Oybek, Selected Works). The lexeme “*ko 'r*” (blinded) have a seme with “unintelligent”, “unconscious”, “ignorant” synonyms.

Synonyms: "1.Full synonymy 2. Traditional synonyms (semantic or idiographic synonyms) 3. Methodological synonyms (stylistic synonyms)" [10, p.7].

In some cases synonymous synonyms and quasi-synonyms (incomplete, inaccurate) synonyms are also presented [1, p 65].

1.Full synonyms can also be traced within polysememic lexis.

In the meanings of result. Augmented, double-worded grammar in synonyms: *go 'shbayram, go 'shaloqbayram.* They describe "what happened simultaneously" in their essay.

It can also be traced within the framework of mobile meanings. *G 'o 'ra* (unripe fruit of the apricot, pike), *go 'r* (raw fruits, melons and watermelons, etc.). So these lexemes are not the same as the main meanings.

In portable terms, it represents the same semema. *Qutilishtadbiriniizlabturganda, g 'o 'raqizyangita 'na, yangio 'pkabilanyigityuraginitirnadi* (M.Ismailiy, "Fergana until morning"). *G 'o 'r bola.* The *g 'o 'ra* and *g 'o 'r* lexemes in these units represent the semantics of “lack of experience in life”.

2. Traditional synonyms. The *achchiq, zahar* lexemes are characterized by "inflammation of the person" and "unpleasantness". In the sentence **Zahar gap** is stronger in meaning.

The semantics of the lexemes can create a series of synonyms based on the similarity or meaning of the semantics, but the polysememic lexis may in some cases not form a series of synonyms.

3. Stylistic synonyms. For example, Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek language [8, p. 52] has three meanings of the word **ayyom** in the first meaning of the word “*kun*” (day), in the second meaning, the word “*bayram*” (holiday), and in the third meaning, the meaning of the “*fasl, vaqt*” (season, time) are meaningful. The script is dedicated to artistic and publicistic styles. *Kun, bayram, fasl, vaqt* (day, holiday, season, and time) are methodological neutral. For example,

1. *Bugunharbirimizuchunqutlug ‘ayyom* (Today is a blessed day for each of us) "Mushtum" (*kun*);
2. *Ayyomingizmuborak* (Happy holiday) (*bayram*);
3. *Bahorayyomidagulgashdetargabirchamanbo ‘lsa...* (Furqat) (*fasl*) (If there is a flower in the spring breeze ... (Furqat) (season). *Yigitlikningayyominiyodqil* (*vaqt*) (Remember the feast of the young man) (A Navy) (time).

"The theory of semantic analysis in synonymy allows for a more accurate description of this phenomenon [7, p.205]. V.D.Chernyak says that the analysis of integral and differential semantic characteristics allows to clarify the characteristics of synonyms and synonyms [10, p. 9].

Learning the synonyms is a matter of synonym for lexeme. As you know, semasiology studies the semantic side of language units. The meaning of the word or additions is called semema. The Semantic semes are divided into the following types by lexical and grammatical meanings:

According to the lexical meaning:

1. Calling seme, nominal semes (denotative semes).
2. Additional meaning semes, iedescription seme.

II. From the point of view of the word morpheme, the semes are divided into the following types:

1. Centralseme.
2. Derivativeseme
3. Relativeseme.
4. Intermediate seme (words from the auxiliary word assert that expressive semeis expressed).

III. Semantic types of seme in the semantic area:

1. Integralseme
2. Differentialeseme
3. Potential seme

IV. Grammatical meaning: 1. Categorical seme. 2. Grammema

V. Seme that generates syntactic relationships: classema.

The synonymy of these semes that are present in semema is formed in the framework of polysememic lexemes:

1. Within the framework of the denotative seme. *Toza, ozoda*.
2. Within the framework of connotative seme. in the sentence *Onamizkeldilar – onamlarkeldilar* created the synonym terms for the ownership and plurality of additions expressed in terms of dignity.
3. In the central seme. For example, *sog'lik, salomatlik; iboli, hayoli*. Such a variety of basic concepts are meaningful in the core syllable.
4. Central and derivative semes. *Kucli, baquvvat* (powerful, energetic) lexemes also exist in the synchronous semes of the central and in the derivative seme. These are some of the grammatical and semantic synonyms.
5. Derivative seme. in the *Odobli, badab* lexemes, possible to observe the meaningful only in the derivative seme.
6. Within the framework of the central and derivatives. *Vahmqaplar – vahimagaplar – vahimaligaplar; bosh tezlik – boshlang'ichtezlik*.
7. In the relative seme: *o'qiyapti, o'qimoqdain* this lexemes is based on the relative seme expressed by modern additions.
8. Within the context of derivat and relative semes. For example, in the *kulgi, kulish* lexemes and syntactic structure appeared in the form of vocabulary formulas. *Anvarkuldi. Ammo bukulish boyaqikulgulardantamoman boshqa, ya'nibeixtiyoriylikkulgusiedi*. (A. Qodiriy, Mehrobdanchayon)
9. According out of semes. M. M. Mirtojiev argues that the auxiliaries and linkers refer to the intermediate term [4, p. 65]. It can be said that meaningfulness can also arise in the context of helpful words. For example, the assistants mean the term "vehicle": *pochtabilanjo 'natdik, pochtaorqalijo 'natdik*.

In the independent vocabularies meaningfulness occurs in the context of lexical meanings. Some of the so-called independent words come as auxiliary and represent grammatical meanings. For example, first, before, when the nose lexeme is exposed, the dennotativesemes will be synonymous. As auxiliary function, grammatical functions accompany grammatical meanings and synonyms in the outer circuits.

Synonymic semes of polysemic lexemes arise in the following terms of the lexemes:

1. In the main meanings: *ayyor, makkor*.
2. Based on the basic and portable meanings: *sag'irlarisemiz* (the main meanings), *sag'irlaribilqillaydi* (portable meaning).

3. The portable meanings: Polyseme syntax and syntax of the lexemes make up synonyms of the lexemes. The proximity in portable meanings creates synonym semes or sememes.

The emergence of mobile meanings is based on the following meanings:

1. Metaphor.
2. Metonymy.
3. Sinekdoxa.
4. Effectiveness.

As is known, synonym lexemes are arise within the context of portable meaning. Therefore, the basis for their occurrence is basically the following:

Metaphor: The lexemes *tilishirin*, *tilishakar* are mean the "pleasant".

Metonymy: The phrase "account" and "pocket" describe the "money" when used in portable terms. *Cho 'ntakchatoq. Endikomandirovkaga ham o 'zhisobingizdanboribkelasimi?* (S.Narov, "Narvon") The *Cho 'ntak* lexeme is used in dialect.

Synecdoche: *Tom*, *hovli*, *eshik*, *ostona* lexemes represent the "home" seme. *Shunda borib, bir tomni ochdi – bari tillaga to 'la, bir tomni ochdi – kumushga to 'la.* ("Ravshan"); *Mirzo Anvar uchto 'rt kundan beri mening hovlimda qo 'nib yurar edi.* (A.Qodiriy "Mehrobdan chayon"); *Eshigini topa olmadingizmi? - Topdim. Aytganingizdek, uning eshigini Toshkentda har kim bilar ekan.* (A.Qodiriy "O'tkan kunlar"); - *Shu er tufayli bizlar sening ostonangga bosh egib, qulluq qilib keldik, - dedi Oyimxon.* (P.Tursun, "O'qituvchi"). *Tom*, *eshik* lexemes using like that meaning is specific to certain dialects. *Tom*, *hovli*, *eshik*, *ostona* lexemes are all parts of the house and all are represented by the section.

4. Figural mean: *Fig'onqilganbundasherlar, Yo'lbars, qoplon, bundaerlar...* "Bahromva Gulandom".

5. In terms of syntactic meaning: *narxibaland, narxiosmonda* lexemes are used in a portable way with "expensive", "high", and thus makes sense.

6. Constructively related meanings. This can be traced in auxiliary words. *Tag-tomir, tag-tub* polysememic lexis is synonymous with semes when used in portable sense. These meaningful words make sense of the whole lexem of the seme series. This should be done with the assistants in grammatical form. *Iloyo, tag-tomir bilan quribketsin bugazandalar!* (I.Rahim, "True Love"). *Zararli illatlarni tag-tub bilan yo 'qotmoq.*

7. According to the occasional meaning. For example, *ko 'pirtirmoq, shishirmoq* lexemes have synonyms. *Aslida bo 'lib o 'tgan voqea ahamiyatsiz bir gap edi. Biroq uni shishirib, ko 'pirtirib yuborish mumkin.* (Said Ahmad, Hukm). *Shishirmoq* and *ko 'pirtirmoq* lexemes have synonyms "compromise".

Polysememe will be able to learn more about the synonymy phenomenon by identifying synonymic seme and sememes within the framework of the lexemes.

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